

Review

The International Conference On The Great Lakes Region (ICGLR): Achievements, Challenges And Prospects

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Abstract

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The paper critically examined the International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR), an association that was formed with the objective of solving conflict issues between member states within the Great Lakes Region, after recognizing the fact that political inability has a considerable regional dimension and thus requires a concerted effort in order to promote sustainable peace and development. It was formed to bring peace among the member states and by doing that, foster development with member states. The paper examined the background of the organization as regard to this objective. In doing that, secondary method of data collection was used to collect data such as articles, books, journals and so on. The paper adopted the theory of liberal Intergovernmentalism and through the aid of this theory, the paper was able to examine the organization while stating its challenges like; member states have not shown enough commitment or willingness to put the Dar-es-Salaam, Nairobi and Addis Ababa agreements into action, financial constraint, and overlapping membership of international organizations and the prospects of the organization. After critical analysis of the International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR), the paper made recommendations like: need for member nations to show more commitment towards the organization in order to implement the Dar-es-Salaam, Nairobi and Addis Ababa agreements into action, and need for the member states to do better in their financial contributions.

Keywords: International, Conference, Great-Lakes, Region and Achievements

INTRODUCTION

In Africa generally and in the Great Lakes region in particular, poverty, weak institutions, and lack of security reforms have affected peace in the region and this has militarized the region (Levine and Nagar, 2015). As a result of the militarized space in the region, economic, political and social activities have been affected and have made people in this region live in perpetual fear and danger as their lives are threatened both by armed groups, sometimes including the security forces of their own governments, and by breakdowns in the ability of states to provide public services and protection from common crime. Iddris and Jobins (2015) argument accentuates this when they argue that twenty five(25) years ago, Rwanda, Burundi and the Democratic

Republic of the Congo (DRC) were engulfed by a series of wars that drew in armies from across the continent, froze economic growth, and triggered some of the worst atrocities seen since the Second World War. According to them, genocide in Rwanda, civil war in Burundi, and the wars and state collapse in the DRC have claimed millions of lives and cost billions of dollars in assistance and lost opportunities. For example, in the Rwanda crisis -,the most notable among the conflicts that have had cross-border impacts or origins, more than 800,000 lives were lost (Kanyangara, 2016). What is clear here is that, in many parts of the region, the fundamental conflict dynamics remain. The collapse of state authority and the prevalence of armed groups have led to local self-

defense militias among others, which have in turn become a source of instability for their communities and their neighbors (Iddris and Jobins, 2015).. Other challenges in the region include forced population movements, arms trafficking, terrorism, organised crime and widespread violence have cross-border causes and consequences and this made the region to be unstable. These conflicts constituted a major threat to international peace and security and due to this; United Nations (UN) and African Union (AU).

Several attempts have been made to addressing the highlighted challenges in terms of exploring and implementing a creative and collective approaches for the prevention, management and resolution of disputes in the region and prevention of conflicts that led to the death of thousands of people in the region. Among such is the establishment of the International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR) in 2004, by 12 nations in this region in collaboration with the United Nations (UN) and African Union (AU). Although the processes began in 2000 when the United Nations Security Council, as stated in its resolutions 1291 and 1304, called for an International Conference on peace, security, democracy and development in the Great Lakes region. Other things that followed was the establishment of the Secretariat of the International Conference in Nairobi, Kenya, under the umbrella of the United Nations and the African Union (Devex.,2020). Apart from its mandate of fostering peace and security in the region, it promotes good governance, promotes democracy and humanitarian and social issues through its protocol on internally displaced persons within the region and also have mandate of promoting gender equality and campaigning against gender based violence.

The problem of this paper therefore is to examine this organisation – the ICGLR with a view of finding out what it has been able to achieve within its operational mandates since its inception in 2004 and as well establish the attendant challenges or problems of the organisation. Also, the work will also proffer suggestions on what the organisation can do to make her better prepared in achieving her objectives despite these challenges.

Theoretical Framework

This work adopts the liberal Inter-governmental theory. Liberal Inter-governmental theory is one of the key theories in the study of regional integration. Inter-governmentalism theory as a regional integration theory was espoused by Stanley Hoffmann in 1966 and further developed by Andrew Moravcsik in the year 1993. This theory according to Olarimiki (2018) sees states and their national governments as the primary actors in the integration process. According to this, it is the government that controls the level and speed of integration.

Nugent cited in Cini (2007) opined that the theory is centered on the view that nation states are the key actors in international affairs and the key political relations between states are channeled primarily via national governments.

The following are the basic assumptions of Inter-governmental theory:

- i. That (at any given moment and in any given issue) varied views about state interests internally and varied actors that represent the state externally aggregate to relatively coherent preference functions and strategic calculations.
- ii. The second basic inter-governmental theory assumption is that states are purposive and at least rational. Rationalism is an individualist or agency assumption: actors calculate the utility of alternative courses of action and choose the one that satisfies (or maximizes) their utility under the circumstances. Agreement to cooperate, or to establish international institutions, is explained as a collective outcome of inter-dependent (strategically) rational state choices realized through intergovernmental negotiation (Moravcsik and Schimmelfennig, 2019).

Inter-governmental theory also argues that one way to restate the states-as-actors and bounded rationality assumptions is that decisions to cooperate internationally can be explained in a three-stage framework: states first define preferences, then bargain to substantive agreements, and finally create (or adjust) institutions to commit to and secure those outcomes in the face of future political uncertainty (Moravcsik, 1989). Furthermore, each stage is distinct and each can be explained by a separate theory. Thus cooperation, or its failure, emerges only at the end of the multiclausal sequence (Moravcsik and Schimmelfennig, 2019). The three-stage framework according to Moravcsik and Schimmelfennig (2019) are;

Forming National Preferences

From the intergovernmental theory perspective, the fundamental goals of states – or ‘state preferences’ – and the strategies they use to achieve them are neither fixed nor uniform: they vary across issues, states and time according to issue-specific societal interdependence and domestic institutions.

Reaching a Substantive Bargain

The national preferences of different states rarely converge precisely. To explain the nature of the substantive policies that emerge from negotiations among states with different preferences, intergovernmental theory deploys (following rationalist institutionalism) a bargaining theory of international cooperation. States must overcome collectively suboptimal outcomes and

achieve coordination or cooperation for mutual benefit, yet at the same time they must decide how the mutual gains of cooperation are distributed among the states. In this context, bargaining theory argues that the outcome of international negotiations, that is, whether and on which terms cooperation comes about, depends on the relative bargaining power of the actors.

Creating Regional Institutions

Given states prepared to strike a substantive agreement to coordinate policy, inter-governmental theory moves into a third stage, in which it seeks to explain the establishment and design of international institutions. To do so, inter-governmental theory relies mainly on a 'regime-theoretical' ('rational' or 'neo-liberal institutionalist') account, which conceives of international institutions as instruments to cope with unintended, unforeseen and often unwanted consequences that arise when states commit to coordinate their policies.

In intergovernmental theory, actors like interest groups and others can influence their government's policies. Domestically, they do not have power to cause their governments to integrate as states are independent decision makers due to the fact that they are legitimate entities (Olarimiki, 2018). Synoptically, inter-governmentalism is about states forming cooperation through preferences, bargain and regional institutions and cooperation by states and can be bilateral, multilateral or tripartite in nature.

Background to the Formation of the Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR)

The ICGLR is an organisation for the countries that exist within the African Great Lakes Region similar to Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) as discussed by Adeniji and Agaba (2014). Interestingly, the name 'Great Lakes Region' was derived from the freshwater lakes and river basins within the central and eastern part of Africa. Great Lakes Region constitutes a complex network of political and economic interactions with significant implications for peace, security and governance (Kanyangara, 2016). Therefore, the International Conference of the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR) is a Conference for the countries located in the east and central Africa – namely Angola, Burundi, Central African Republic, Republic of Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Republic of South Sudan, Sudan, Tanzania and Zambia. In other words, the ICGLR is a regional organisation stretching over Central, Eastern and Southern Africa with twelve diverse member states, several of which are characterised by war, conflict, mistrust and mutual tensions about resources and border lines. That is, it is a

region with interlinked conflicts and common fundamental problems that emanate from post-colonial challenges to state-building and nation-building. But among its membership, ICGLR also counts states which are rather stable and secure and on a path towards further development and prosperity (Hauck, 2017).

Several factors rooted deep in historical issues of protracted cross-border and internal conflicts traceable back to the pre-colonial history of the region, strongly reinforced through the decisions made during the Africa Conference in Berlin, 1885, all together with the crisis in eastern part of DRC, the Rwanda genocide and its effect among others informed the establishment of the ICGLR. In the words of Hauck (2017:6), while commenting on what informed the establishment of the ICGLR posits that:

At the root of the foundation of the ICGLR lie the conflicts in eastern DRC and its neighboring countries in the post-cold war 1990s with hundreds of thousands of deaths. First, there were the consequences of the 1994 genocide in Rwanda of almost one million persons dead while another two million were pushed to leave the country by the Government and its army and militia who executed the genocide. The presence of thousands of Rwandese refugees as well as armed soldiers and militias mainly in the DRC was a threat to the regional security, requiring a regional solution. Second, there was a need for an agreement to end the political crisis and the war in the DRC where many countries were involved in what some observers called "the first African World War" in 1998. Indeed, at the end of the 1990s, DRC was divided into three zones, one (West) under Kinshasa government control supported by Angola, Zimbabwe and Namibia; the second (East) by a rebel movement (Congolese Rally for Democracy - RCD), supported by Rwanda (and somehow by Burundi); and third (North) by another rebel movement, the Movement for the Liberation of the Congo (MLC) supported by Uganda.

It is also argued that apart from the crisis in Rwanda which flowed into the eastern part of DRC, armed conflicts also took place in eight of the twelve ICGLR's countries in the years prior to the conference. These conflicts nevertheless had spill-over effects such as flows of refugees and arms trade, which in turn contributed to destabilization in neighbouring countries (Heyle, 2010).

With this, the United Nations (UN) and the OAU (Organisation of the African Unity, predecessor of the African Union) using the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) and the Secretary General of the UN (UNSG) adopted a resolutions- 1291 and 1304 respectively in February and June 2000 calling for a holding, if conditions were appropriate, an international conference on peace, security, democracy and development in the Great Lakes Region under the auspices of the UN and the OAU (Hauck, 2017). In November 2004, the twelve Heads of State and Government of the member countries unanimously adopted the Declaration on Peace, Security and Development in the Great Lakes region in Dar es

Salaam, Tanzania. This Dar-es-Salaam Declaration presented a political statement with the intention to address the root causes of intractable conflicts and constraints to development in a regional and innovative approach. The Heads of State and Government convened once again in Nairobi in 2006 to sign the Pact on Security, Stability and Development in the Great Lakes Region. The Pact included the Dar es Salaam Declaration, Programmes of Action and Protocols. (www.icglr.org)

The Dar-es-Salaam declaration was also done to show the desire of the organization in bringing development in the region. The key extracts from the Dar-es-Salaam declaration peace and security; to promote peace and security in the region which will in turn bring about development in the region

- a) democracy and good governance; to promote democracy in the region by monitoring elections so as to ensure that elections conducted by member states are free and fair
- b) economic development and regional integration; creating policies that will bring economic development in the region and also integrate member states through unity and
- c) humanitarian and social matters. The declaration also provided for the creation of a special fund for reconstruction and development in the Great Lakes region. The Declaration of Dar-es-Salaam showed a strong commitment to peace in the region (Kyangara, 2016)

To strengthen the ideals of the peace, stability and development in the region, the Heads of State and Government of the region convened once again in Nairobi in 2006 to sign the Pact on Security, Stability and Development in the Great Lakes Region. The pact was signed precisely signed 15 December 2006. It is known as the Nairobi Pact; it came into effect on 21 June 2008 after its ratification by eight of the 12 member states' parliaments. The pact embodies the desire of the heads of state to solve the region's problems, and its objectives include:

- a) carrying out the proposals in the Declaration of Dar-es-Salaam, the agreements, the action programmes, the regional follow-up mechanism and the special fund for reconstruction and development; and
- b) the creation of conditions of security, stability and sustainable development between the member states. The Summit of Heads of State and Government meet every second year and oversees the implementation of the pact (www.icglr.org)

Since the signing of the Nairobi Pact, the heads of state and government have taken turns to chair the body; the Nairobi Pact contains 10 protocols, action programmes and projects. It places special emphasis on non-aggression and mutual defense in the Great Lakes region (Protocol 5). According to Protocol 5, the member states commit themselves to maintaining peace and

security and, in particular not to resort to force to resolve their differences; when there is dispute between the member states, peaceful means should be used to resolve the conflict and not force; not to support (directly or indirectly) armed groups based in the territory of another state nor to allow on their territory armed groups engaged in armed conflicts against the government of another state; and to cooperate to disarm and break up existing rebel groups.

The Objective of the International Conference on The Great Lakes Region

according to Kyangara (2016) is to initiate a process within which the leaders of the countries of the Great Lakes region will try to come to a common agreement on a number of principles such as;

- a) Good neighbourly relations: one of the key objectives of the body is to promote good neighbourly relations and this will ensure that there is no interstate conflict over boundary or other issues between the member states of the regional organization.
- b) Stability, peace and development: this will enable the organization to specify and implement a number of action programmes with a view to ending the cycle of conflict and leading the region towards lasting peace, stability, security, democracy and development'
- c) To promote Democracy in the region: this is to promote democracy in the region so as to ensure that there is respect for human rights, accountability and rule of law and good governance in the region.

Decision Making Bodies of the ICGLR

- i. The Heads of State and Government Summit – it is the Supreme decision making organ of the conference. The organ is responsible for all the decision making that guide the operations of the regional organization. The organ provides political direction that guide the body. It is chaired by a head of state of member states and leadership of this organ is based on rotation.
- ii. The Regional Inter-Ministerial Committee (RIMC) - the committee is made up of foreign ministers of member states. The committee is responsible for development of protocols and legal decision framework and also agenda for the submit. It guides the head of states and governments on strategic decisions.
- iii. National Coordination and Collaboration Mechanism - the mechanism provide link between regional and respective national operations of the ICGLR. It ensures that its members are fully involved in the matters of the organization by identifying new issues and further developing the existing ones.
- iv. The Executive Secretariat – this organ of the body is responsible for coordinating the activities of the organi-

zation. The Secretariat provides technical functions of the body and is headed by executive secretary; the Secretariat is responsible for the calendar events of the organization and its located in Bujumbura.

Divisions of ICGLR

The main divisions of ICGLR are

- i. Peace and Security- this division of the body is responsible for promoting peace and security in the region
- ii. Democracy and Good Governance- this division of the regional body deals with the promotion of good governance and entrenchment of democratic ideals in the region
- iii. Economic Development and Regional Integration- the division is about policies that brings economic development and integration in the region.
- iv. Humanitarian and Social Issues- it handles issues like gender equality and internally displaced person's crisis.

As obtained on the ICGLR websites (www.icglr.org), the ICGLR also addresses other critical and serious issues on the region. Such issues include Gender, Environment, Human Rights, HIV/AIDS and Human Settlements.

It is noteworthy to state the guiding principles of the approach of the conference. There are two main principles that guide the approach of the ICGLR. First, a sustainable solution for peace, stability and development in the Great Lakes Region has to be based on strong ownership of the countries of this region themselves. Second, the ICGLR is based on partnership with stakeholders, in particular the Group of Friends and Special Envoys which provides financial, diplomatic, technical and political support.

The Group of Friends and Special Envoys is co-chaired by Canada and the Netherlands. Its member countries and organisations include Austria, Belgium, Canada, China, Denmark, the European Union, Finland, France, Gabon, Germany and Greece. Others are the Holy See, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kuwait, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Norway, Portugal, Russia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States of America.

In order to ensure the rightful implementation of its projects and protocols the ICGLR brings together experts and authorities from its Member Countries to meet on a regular basis. Twice every year, the Regional Inter-Ministerial Committee (RIMC) as Executive board of the ICGLR to assess the progress that has been made. The Summit of Heads of State which is the supreme organ takes place at least once every two years. In case of emergency the Chair of the Summit may call for an extraordinary Summit of the Troika. This emergency caucus comprises the Chair of the Summit, his/her

predecessor and his/her successor and thus includes representatives of three member countries.

On the national level, each of the Member States has put in place a National Coordination Mechanism (NCM) also including representatives of civil society, women and youth in order to ensure the follow up and implementation of decisions made by the Summit and the RIMC.

Humanitarian and Social Issues

Achievements and Progress of the International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR)

According to Karamira (2016) and David (2020), the achievements of International Conference on the Great Lakes region include:

- i. The Conference Secretariat has established itself as a regional mediator between the various national interests of the signatory states, offering an urgently-needed platform for regional networking through its bodies and through regular meetings. The platform provided by the conference has given the member states the avenue to deliberate on key issues and this has helped to reduce tension in the region.
- ii. With its Regional Initiative against the illegal Exploitation of Natural Resources, ICGLR has created an important policy and action framework to prevent trade in conflict resources. In Rwanda and the Democratic Republic of Congo, legislation has been aligned and the Regional Certification Mechanism has been successfully implemented. These developments are also progressing in other member states and are gradually being incorporated into national legislation. The work of the technical unit in implementing the Initiative is perceived as supportive by the relevant ministries.
- iii. Since the creation ICGLR, peace and security has improved relatively compared to when the body was not in existence. Rwanda genocide of 1994 and the Congo crisis as well as others increased call for the creation of ICGLR and since its creation, such killings have reduced.
- iv. The International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR) has promoted good governance in the region as well as democratic ideals. The body monitor elections conducted by the member states to ensure that they are free and fair and to some extent. There has been progress made as some member states have seen peaceful transition of power like Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). The country witness peaceful transition of power when former president, Joseph Kabila, that ruled Congo for decades handed over power to Félix Tshisekedi, the man that won election in 2018. Also in Burundi, Évariste Ndayishimiye won elections in 2020 after late president Pierre Nkurunziza ruled for almost 15 years.
- v. The International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR) has promoted gender equality in the

region and has championed women's right through the creation of Regional Women Forum (RWF), created in December 2010 by ministers in charge of gender/ feminine issues from 11 member states. This forum is one of the most active and important forum of ICGLR and have promoted women's rights in the region.

Problems and Prospects of ICGLR

According to Kanyangara (2016), some of the problems of ICGLR includes:

(a) international conference on the Great Lakes Region members have not shown enough commitment in the implementation of the Dar-es-Salaam, Nairobi and Addis Ababa agreements into action - Member states have not shown willingness and eagerness to implement the aims, objectives of these agreements and this is a major challenge to the body and if this is addressed, the body will do better.

(b) Financial constraints - this is one of the major challenges facing the body and has contributed to the inadequate implementation of the Dar-es-Salaam, Nairobi and Addis Ababa agreements into action. The ICGLR relies on the financial contribution of member states and partners to effect its programmes and projects. when financial contributions fail to come or come in limited manner, it affects the projects of the body. Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) has never honored its annual contribution, While Rwanda and Burundi have outstanding debts Mugabe (2010) cited in Nzaramba (2012).

(c) new and persistent conflicts – conflicts such as those in South Sudan, Central African Republic, the DRC and Burundi continue to characterise the region. These conflicts undermine the region's capacity for conflict management and resolution and this constitute a major challenge to the body.

(d) limited partnership with civil society organizations (CSO's) - ICGLR has not effectively partner with CSO's and this reflected in some of its key documents and policy plans.

(e) overlapping membership of regional organizations - Member nations belong to different regional organizations and this brings about divided loyalty and commitment issue. Some countries like Rwanda, Uganda, Kenya etc are members of COMESA while some are members of IGAD like Sudan, Uganda, Kenya and others.

ICGLR as an organization have challenges as pointed out above but if efforts are made to ameliorate these challenges, the organization stand a greater chance of actualizing its mandate of fostering peace, development and good governance among the member nations.

CONCLUSION

The International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR), created in 2004 by 11 member states have contributed to development, fostering of peace and security in the Great Lakes Region since its creation. The organization was created in order to explore and implement creative and collective approaches for the prevention, management and resolution of disputes in the region and prevention of conflicts, promotion of good governance and entrenchment of democratic ideals as well as gender equality in the region. This organization has made some achievements like serving as mediator between member states, initiative against illegal exploration of natural resources, promotion of good governance and others but the organization is not without some challenges. Some of the challenges International Conference on the Great Lakes Region (ICGLR) is facing includes financial limitation, commitment issue, overlapping membership, inadequate coordination with CSOs etcetera and if some of these issues facing the body are addressed, the body will be more effective and will do better that what it has done.

RECOMMENDATIONS

(a) need for member nations to show more commitment - Member states need to show more commitment towards the organization by implementing the Dar-es-Salaam, Nairobi and Addis Ababa agreements.

(b) need for member states to do better in their financial contributions - the member states need to contribute more financially as inadequate finance have affected the organization and some of its projects have been abandoned due to that.

(c) to address the issue of inadequate coordination with civil society organizations (CSOs), The ICGLR should actively involve CSO experts on specific issues in the run-up to major meetings and policy processes.

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